

ON THE ACTIVATION OF PAPAIN

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The rate of activation of papain by sodium thiosulphate has been further increased by incorporation of 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Papain is one of the common proteolytic enzymes used in the general hydrolysis of protein substances. As available in the market, it is not so active and accordingly, its proteolytic activity is generally enhanced by incorporation of some reducing substances. In the breakdown of animal protein, like muscle tissue, the glutathion or the cystine molecule present in the substrate often behaves as an activator (*cf.* Gottschall, *Food Research*, 1944, 9, 6). Brewer (*J. Bact.*, 1943, 46, 395) has used sodium sulphide in preparing a bacteriological medium for a papain-protein digest. Recently Basu *et al* (*Ind. Med. Gaz.*, 1945, 80, 398) have activated papain by sodium thiosulphate in preparing culture medium from ground nut. Even activation does not increase the proteolytic activity to the degree that may be obtained by using trypsin. In connection with certain other investigations that are being followed in this laboratory, enhancement of the rate as well as the degree of digestion of protein bodies by papain are highly desirable. As such a work was undertaken to find a clue to its proteolytic activity and the factors on which the latter may depend.

Various hypotheses are being put forward (*cf.* Willstätter, Kuhn and Sobotka, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 138, 184; Waldschmidt-Leitz *et al*, *ibid.*, 1933, 214, 75; Ganapati and Sastri, *Biochem J.*, 1939, 33, 1175; Giri and Seshagirirao, *Science & Culture*, 1942, 7, 408) from time to time for the factors that are responsible for the proteolytic activity of commercial papain. Anson (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 135, 797) finds that heavy metal impurities catalyse the oxidation of protein-SH group, as present in papain, by oxygen or an oxidisable matter. Iron and/or copper may also act as an oxidase catalyst (*cf.* also Hofstede, *Quart. J. Pharm. & Pharmacol.*, 1930, 3, 103). The influence of a reducing agent in restoring or enhancing the activity of papain may be due to the conversion of the oxidised complex as present in the enzyme. Copper, which is again known to lower this enzymatic activity, may exert its characteristic action by catalysing the oxidation of ferrous ion to the ferric state. On this hypothesis the activity of papain may be further increased by incorporating a suitable reagent capable of removing the iron oxidase during the enzymatic fission. A reagent like this is found in 8-hydroxyquinoline which is known to react with iron salts to form insoluble compounds and thereby may remove them from the phase of enzymic action. This may further potentiate any di-enol oxidation-reduction group if present in the enzyme (*cf.* Giri and Seshagirirao, *loc. cit*; and Lyman, Schultze and King, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 116, 563). This expectation has been fully realised and the data collected in the course of these investigations are being recorded in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Substrate.—Casein (commercial variety) of known composition was taken in 500 c. c. distilled water and heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on a boiling water-bath. This was then mixed with a few c. c. of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution to afford an almost uniform solution and heated further for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. This resulted in a milky solution of pH 5.0.

Enzyme.—Papain (Ceylon variety, 2.4 g.) was taken in 25 c. c. water and mixed with 25 c. c. of a 4.8% solution of sodium thiosulphate (chemically pure). The whole was then left aside at room temperature (26°) for about 1 hour.

In another flask a similar mixture was further incorporated with an alcoholic solution (5 c. c.) of 8-hydroxyquinoline (4.8%).

Digestion.—This was carried with the casein substrate at 50° in an incubator. The substrate was taken separately in four different 100 c. c. flasks, and treated with the enzyme preparations.

(a) Papain alone; (b) papain mixed with sodium thiosulphate as mentioned above; (c) the enzyme solution containing papain-sodium thiosulphate-8-hydroxyquinoline; and (d) a fresh alcoholic extract of pancreas. The proportion of the enzyme to the protein (casein) was always 1 : 25, and the final volume of the digestion mixture was so adjusted that the concentration of the substrate (casein) remained about 10%.

The flasks were then placed in the incubator and were shaken occasionally. The rate of digestion was followed up to 48 hours. From time to time 2 c. c. of the suspension were taken out, boiled, cooled, and filtered. The clear filtrate was titrated against 0.1*N*-alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution in presence of excess of alcohol using thymolphthalein as indicator (*cf.* Willstätter and Waldschmidt-Leitz., *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 2988). The results are recorded below.

TABLE I

Figures indicate the number of c. c. of 0.1 *N*-KOH per 2 c. c. of the digest.

Period of digestion.	Papain alone (control)	Enzyme Papain Activated with thio.	Papain Activated with thio and oxy- quinoline.	Enzyme Trypsin (Alcoholic solution)
2 hours.	0.8	1.5	2.44	2.6
4	1.2	1.9	2.21	3.1
6	1.5	2.3	...	3.6
8	1.7	2.5	...	3.8
24	2.6	3.1	4.37	4.4
28	2.7	3.1	4.37	4.4
30	2.7	3.15	...	4.5
46	4.56	...
48	3.2	3.30	4.68	4.7

From the figures in Table I it is evident that the amount of liberated carboxyl group, as measured by using the Willstätter technique from the protein casein under the influence of the enzyme papain at varying conditions, is not the same. The degree of digestion in the case when papain has been activated by sodium thiosulphate with 8-hydroxyquinoline compares even fairly with that brought about by the help of the enzyme trypsin. 8-Hydroxyquinoline alone exerts only a slight activating influence on the proteolytic activity of papain.

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